

1-Alkyl-substituted 2,4-Dithiobiurets and Related Thiurets : Interaction of Aliphatic Amines and Isopersulphocyanic Acid

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Preparation of a number of 1-alkyl-substituted 2, 4-dithiobiurets by the action of aliphatic amines on isopersulphocyanic acid has been described. Related thiurets have also been obtained by their oxidation.

1-Aryl-substituted 2, 4-dithiobiurets (I) are easily obtained by the action of aromatic amines on isopersulphocyanic acid (Glutz, *Annalen*, 1870, 154, 44; Fromm *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1893, 275, 34; 1908, 361, 319; 1906, 348, 167, 173; *Ber.*, 1895, 28, 1099; Tursini, *Ber.*, 1884, 17, 585, 586).

Alkyl analogues of the dithiobiurets, only a few of which are known (Hecht, *Ber.*, 1892, 25, 753, 754), appear to have been obtained, however, by the action of hydrogen sulphide on the related *N*-alkyl-*N'*-cyanothiocarbamides (Wunderlich, *Ber.*, 1886, 19, 449; Hecht, *loc. cit.*, p.753). This last group of compounds has not been sufficiently well characterised, and what is more, experience has shown that addition of hydrogen sulphide is not quite as easy to accomplish as hydrolysis. Consequently, the yields are poor and the method entails a heavy loss of expensive starting materials like alkyl isothiocyanates.

The interaction of aliphatic amines and isopersulphocyanic acid, which does not appear to have been studied hitherto, has therefore been investigated in the hope of extending it to the preparation of 1-alkyl-substituted 2, 4-dithiobiurets. The reaction is found, at ordinary temperatures, analogous to that with aromatic amines, and it affords 1-alkyl-substituted 2, 4-dithiobiurets in good yields. When the reaction was carried out at higher temperatures (water bath) sulphur, aminethiocyanate, H₂S, etc. were obtained instead of the expected dithiobiuret, which was undoubtedly formed as the primary product but later was decomposed.

Like the aromatic derivatives (Fromm *et al.*, *Ber.*, 1895, 28, 1100; *Annalen*, 1893, 275, 42; 1906, 348, 161; 1907, 356, 179; 1908, 361, 320; 1912, 394, 260, 265) 1-alkyl-substituted 2, 4-dithiobiurets are easily oxidised in an acidic medium to the related thiurets (II).

EXPERIMENTAL

Formation of 1-Alkyl-substituted 2, 4-Dithiobiurets.—Isopersulphocyanic acid and a strong aqueous solution of the desired amine were mixed at ordinary temperature. The reaction mixture warmed on stirring; the persulphocyanic acid went gradually into solution, followed by precipitation of elemental sulphur, which was subsequently filtered off. The filtrate was then left to stand at ordinary temperature, when crystals of the appropriate dithiobiuret (often mixed with elemental sulphur) began to separate. The reaction took generally 36 to 72 hours for completion and the product was collected thereafter. The crude product after being dried was washed with a little carbon disulphide, which removed the accompanying sulphur. It was crystallised from water, dilute ethanol, or rectified spirit, as was found convenient. The reaction was carried out with methyl-, dimethyl-, ethyl-, propyl-, butyl-, and benzyl- amines. In every case the related dithiobiuret was obtained. The results are summarised in Table I.

TABLE I
Isopersulphocyanic acid used = 10 g.

Expt. No.	Amines used.	Product formed.	M.P.	Formula.	Found.	Calc.
1.	Methylamine (20 c.c. of 33% aq. soln.)	1-methyl-D*-(5.5g.)	153°	$C_2H_7N_2S_2$	C: 24.22% H: 4.82 N: 27.94 S: 42.88	24.16% 4.69 28.18 42.95
2.	Ethylamine (30 c.c. of 33% aq. soln.)	1-Ethyl-D** (1st crop 4 g.; 2nd crop 0.5 g., pale yellow crystals)	+178° +129°	$C_4H_{11}N_2S_2$	C: 30.06 H: 5.71 N: 25.56 S: 39.52	29.44 5.52 25.76 39.26
3.	Ethylamine (20 c.c. of 33% aq. soln.)	Do. Major part	129°	$C_4H_{11}N_2S_2$	C: 29.32 H: 5.34 N: 25.28 S: 39.48	29.44 5.52 25.76 39.26
4.	Propylamine (35 c.c. of 40% aq. soln.)	1-Propyl-D* (3.5g.)	121°	$C_6H_{13}N_2S_2$	C: 34.32 H: 6.15 N: 23.56 S: 35.88	33.89 6.21 23.72 36.15
5.	Butylamine (40 c.c. of 33% aq. soln.)	1-Butyl-D (3.5g.)	115°	$C_8H_{17}N_2S_2$	C: 37.91 H: 6.89 N: 21.85 S: 33.79	37.69 6.80 21.98 33.50
6.	Benzylamine (15 g. in ethanol, 30 c.c.)	1-Benzyl-D				
7.	Dimethylamine (25 c.c. of 40% aq. soln.)	1-Dimethyl-D (5.0 g.)	131°	$C_4H_{11}N_2S_2$		

Precipitated on acidification as a sticky solid which could not be crystallised; but the product was identified (vide Table II).

* Hecht, *Ber.*, 1892, 25, 753, 754.

** Hecht (*loc. cit.*) gives m.p. 175°.

† These were probably dimorphous forms. Both gave the same thiuret on oxidation (vide Table II).
N.B.—D denotes 2,4-dithiobiurets.

Oxidation of 1-Alkyl-substituted 2, 4-Dithiobiurets: Formation of the Related Thiurets (5-Alkylamino-3-imino-1, 2, 4-dithioazolidines).—A small quantity (2-3 g.) of the dithiobiuret was dissolved in ethanol (10-20 c.c.) and iodine in aqueous potassium iodide solution was added gradually with stirring till the pale yellow colour of the reaction mixture persisted. During addition of iodine or on cooling, after excess of iodine had been added, crystals began to separate. The last trace of unchanged iodine was removed by adding a little of bisulphite solution. The product was collected and crystallised from hot water or ethanol. In every case, it was found to be the hydriodide of the base. The results are presented in Table II.

TABLE II

Expt. No.	Dithiobiuret oxidised.	5-Alkylamino-3-imino-1, 2, 4-dithioazolidine hydriodide formed.	M.P.	Formula.	Found.	Calc.
1.	1-Methyl-	5-Methylamino-	204°	C ₄ H ₈ N ₂ IS ₂	C: 13.14% H: 2.44 N: 15.08 S: 22.92	13.09% 2.18 15.27 23.27
2.	1-Ethyl-	5-Ethylamino-	144°	C ₆ H ₁₂ N ₂ IS ₂	C: 17.70 H: 3.14 N: 14.58 S: 22.38	16.60 2.76 14.53 22.14
3.	1-Propyl ^a -	5-Propyl ^a amino-	131-32°	C ₈ H ₁₆ N ₂ IS ₂	C: 19.88 H: 3.47 N: 13.82 S: 21.48	19.80 3.30 13.86 21.12
4.	1-Butyl ^a -	5-Butyl ^a amino-	121°	C ₈ H ₁₆ N ₂ IS ₂	C: 22.93 H: 3.82 N: 13.30 S: 20.12	22.71 3.78 13.24 20.18
5.	1-Benzyl-	5-Benzylamino-	184-85°	C ₉ H ₁₀ N ₂ IS ₂	C: 31.72 H: 2.86 N: 12.16 S: 18.46	30.76 2.84 11.96 18.23
6.	1-Dimethyl-	5-Dimethylamino-	194°	C ₆ H ₈ N ₂ IS ₂	C: 15.85 H: 3.18 N: 14.13 S: 22.45	16.60 2.76 14.53 22.14

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